

FORMING OF PREPREG COMPOSITE PARTS WITH ALIGNED MULTI WALL CARBON NANOTUBES

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Abstract

A well known problem for Carbon Nano Tubes (CNT) is the dispersion and distribution of the CNTs into the resin during the mixing process. By using more structured CNTs, as in highly aligned multiwall carbon nanotubes (MWCNT), better results in terms of dispersion and distribution is obtained. This work investigates the influence of a UD-prepreg composite manufacturing process on the aligned MWCNTs. The investigation shows that aligned MWCNTs could be processed without significant deformation at least if the forming mechanisms are known and controlled.

1 Introduction

During the latest decade different ways of mixing carbon nanotubes (CNT) into thermoset resins have been explored with the purpose to improve different physical properties [1] such as electrical conductivity [2], thermal conductivity and mechanical properties [3]. A well known problem with the mixing process is the dispersion and distribution of the CNTs into the resin, where a poor dispersion diminishes the effects of the CNT material. By using more structured CNTs, as in highly aligned multiwall carbon nanotubes (MWCNT) [4], [5], [6] better results in terms of dispersion and distribution are obtained. Aligned CNTs introduced in the interlaminar region of prepreg materials have been shown to increase mechanical properties including interlaminar toughness [7] and in-plane strengths [8].

Aligned MWCNTs can be grown by thermal catalytic chemical vapor deposition (CVD) on silicon wafers using a thin catalyst layer of Fe/Al₂O₃ deposited by electron beam evaporation. CNT growth is typically performed in a tube furnace at atmospheric pressure using ethylene as the carbon source. The resulting materials have the appearance of a mat with out-of-plane aligned MWCNTs, that

can be transferred to a carbon/epoxy prepreg surface and used as an interlayer between the carbon fibre layers in a stacked prepreg laminate.

A lot of research has been done in the field of improving the growth process of aligned MWCNTs [9], [10], [11] but very little research has been performed on processing of the composite including MWCNTs on the surface of the carbon /epoxy prepreg layers inside the stack. In the composite manufacturing process the MWCNTs might be affected in all process operations, in specific during the lay-up, forming and cure process.

In the prepreg lay-up process there always exist some debulking operations with purpose to transport entrapped air out of the laminate minimizing the bulk factor (difference between lay-up thickness and cured ply thickness (CPT)). Typically this debulking process is performed every fourth ply in vacuum bag. Both compaction and shear are introduced during the lay-up due to the debulk operation.

Forming of a pre-stacked prepreg laminate requires that the material undergoes different forming mechanisms, such as intraply shear, interply shear, ply bending, intraply axial loading and compaction/consolidation [12]. It is an assumption that aligned MWCNTs are sensitive to several of the mechanisms above. A previous work on FE-simulations on the forming process [13] of a spar with recess geometry (see figure 1), shows that different spar areas with different lay-up are experiencing different degrees of in-plane shear during forming. Figure 2 show the in-plane shear in the forming simulation of the spar mentioned above with a [-45/45/90/0/90] lay-up. As seen in figure 2 most shear appears in the [-45] layer in the spar recess area.

Simplified, the material transportation in UD prepreg during curing includes fibre bed compaction and resin infiltration [14]. Use of a non bleed net resin prepreg system limits the interply resin flow during the cure process while a free bleed of the resin out of the laminate increases the interply resin flow.

The aim of this work is to investigate the influence of the composite manufacturing process on the aligned MWCNT. The studied process is a Hot Drap Forming process (HDF) using a multi-stacked Uni-directional (UD) carbon/epoxy prepreg, where the MWCNTs are placed at different positions on the spar.

2 Experimental

The study was performed on a spar with recess geometry (see figure 1 and table 1). Based on previous work on FE-simulations on the forming process [13], areas experiencing different degrees of shear during forming of the part were selected. Aligned MWCNTs [4], [8] approximately of height 20 microns were applied in the interlayers (in accordance with table 2) of the multi-stacked prepreg at these areas. Further, flat specimens as well as an area on the spar where no shear was expected to occur, were used as references. The part was cured after forming. Evaluation of the MWCNTs was performed using a Scanning Electron Micrograph (SEM) with the aim to detect deformations in the aligned MWCNT interlayers due to forming.

2.1 Material

A 180°C cure epoxy prepreg with HT carbon fibre and approximately 57% fibre volume content was used in the experiments. The epoxy had a CPT of 0.131 mm and did not contain any thermoplastic toughener particles in the matrix.

2.2 MWCNT transfer

Aligned MWCNTs were transferred from the silicon wafers to the prepreg surface by using a vacuum bag with controlled vacuum level and a heat source controlled by thermocouples. The sample was moderately heated during the MWCNT transfer.

2.3 Lay-up

Three different types of lay-ups were used in the experimental study to investigate the influence of the composite manufacturing process on the aligned MWCNT: A=[-45, 45], sheet size 100 x 100 mm, with purpose to investigate the influence of lay-up on a flat sample, B=[-45, 45, 90, 0, 90]_s, sheet size 100 x 100 mm, with purpose to investigate the influence of cure on a flat sample and C=[-45, 45, 90, 0, 90], sheet size 180 x 480 mm, with purpose to investigate the influence of forming, see table 2. The fibre directions in sample C are defined in figure 3. Debulking during lay-up was performed with a vacuum bag procedure.

2.4 Forming of spars

The spars were formed from flat laminas stacked according to the test matrix, table 2. The following HDF process was used; The pre-stacked lamina was placed on top of the mould, where after the vacuum bag was loosely sealed on top of the lamina. After heating up to 65°C, vacuum was applied forcing the material to form towards the mould. The vacuum was held until the lamina temperature was at room temperature.

2.5 Cure assembly

Sample A1 was free standing and no cure assembly was used. Sample B1 was sealed with tape (see figure 6) at the laminate edges to minimize the interply resin flow during the cure cycle. The cure assembly for sample B2 allowed free bleed (see figure 6) with purpose to maximize the interply resin flow during the cure cycle. Sample C1 was sealed with tape at the laminate edges (equal to sample B1).

2.6 Cure

Sample A1 was cured with free standing isothermal 180°C cure cycle with a 2h hold. This cure cycle was chosen to minimize the cure effect on the lay-up results. Sample B1, B2 and C1 were cured in an autoclave with the following typical aerospace cure cycle: heating (1.5°C/min) to 180°C, 2h hold followed by cooling (3°C/min).

2.7 Experimental verification

Experimental verification was performed using a Scanning Electron Micrograph (SEM) to look for deformations, in the aligned MWCNT interlayer's. The micrograph sections in sample A1, B1 and B2 were cut from mid MWCNT area along the [0]

direction. The micrograph sections in sample C1 area L were cut 20 mm from the edge along [90] direction and the micrograph sections in sample C1 area J were cut 20 mm from the edge along [0] direction.

3 Results

Results from the SEM evaluation of the MWCNT areas in the samples are presented in Table 3. The deformation modes detected are schematically shown figure 7. The figures are clarifications of the SEM graphs which are not included here.

Sample A1 which was free standing cured lay-up tests, showed limited buckling and local shear in the MWCNT interlayer but none of the samples showed shear deformation of type 1 to 4 or combination of mechanisms.

Sample B1 and B2, which were cured with a non bleed and a bleed cure assembly, showed limited buckling and local shear in the MWCNT interlayer but none of the samples showed shear deformation of type 1 to 4 or combination of mechanisms.

Sample C1 area L, which were cut from the spar web, showed buckling and local shear in MWCNT interlayer but not shear deformation of type 1 to 4 or combination of mechanisms.

Sample C1.2 and C1.3 area J, which were cut from the recess area, showed a combination of shear deformation type 1 to 3 and combination of mechanisms in the MWCNT interlayer's between the [-45] and the [45] layer were most shear during forming was expected.

Sample C1.1 area J, which were cut from the recess area, showed shear induced slip lines (shear type 4) in the MWCNT interlayer's (between [-45] and [45] layer) were most shear during forming was expected. Sample C1.1 area J also showed shear deformation type 3 between the [-45] and the [45] layer.

4 Discussion

Sample A1 shows that it is not likely that shear deformations (of type 1 to 4) in the MWCNT interlayer will appear during the lay-up process. These samples also show that the only influence of lay-up process on the MWCNT interlayer is a

limited buckling and local shear deformation (see figure 7a and 7b).

In sample B2 a cure assembly was chosen that allowed free bleed of resin out of the laminate with the purpose to maximize the interply resin flow. The result of this sample was compared with the result of sample B1 which did not allow any bleed out of the laminate with the purpose to minimize the interply resin flow. The samples showed that it is not likely that shear deformations (of type 1 to 4) in the MWCNT interlayer arise from the interply resin flow. Both samples showed limited buckling and local shear deformation in the MWCNT interlayer. Comparing samples A1, B1 and B3 the cure cycle seems to have a limited effect on the MWCNT interlayer deformation.

Sample C1 area L was expected to experience low degree of shear during forming. This was also seen in the results since no shear deformation (of type 1 to 4) appeared in the MWCNT interlayer in this section. Some buckling and local shear deformation in the MWCNT interlayer did appear in sample C1. Based on the results of all samples (A1, B1, B2 and C1) limited buckling and local shear deformation might be introduced in either the lay-up, forming or the cure process.

Sample C1 area J was expected to experience high degree of shear during forming. This was also seen in the results since shear deformation did appear in the MWCNT interlayer in this section. In some cases areas were found with pulled apart aligned MWCNT areas (see figure 7g). This was considered to be a combination of deformation mechanisms and not as pure shear. In sample C1.1 area J, shear induced slip lines (shear type 4) in the MWCNT interlayer also appeared. This might depend on the level of resin impregnation in the MWCNT interlayer before forming. Shear type 4 seems less likely to happen than shear type 1 to 3 and is therefore just considered as an observation.

The investigation shows that aligned MWCNTs could be processed without significant deformation at least if the forming mechanisms are known and controlled. Taking all results in consideration it seems like the aligned MWCNTs can be used as a visual indicator of in plane shear in the forming process that otherwise is not detectable, at least in

laminate areas which experience high degree of shear during forming. This far, no attempts have been made trying to measure the influence of the deformation of the MWCNTs on the properties of the CNT reinforced CFRP.

5 Conclusions

The present work aimed to investigate the influence of the composite manufacturing process on the aligned MWCNT, including lay-up, forming and cure. The study showed that shear deformation did appear in the MWCNT interlayer when the interlayer was expected to experience high degree of shear during forming. Shear deformations (except local shear) in the MWCNT interlayer did not appear during the lay-up or cure. The study also showed that limited buckling deformation can occur in the MWCNT interlayer during the lay-up, forming or cure process.

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7 References

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Table 1 Spar geometry

Spar length [mm]	480
Web width [mm]	70
Flange length [mm]	55
Transition zone length [mm]	125
Recess depth [mm]	6.25
Nominal thickness [mm]	0.655
Radius recess flange [mm]	2
Radius Straight flange [mm]	6

Table 2 Process parameters

Sample ID	Sample geometry	Lay-up	MWCNT placement	Cure assembly	Cure	No. of trials
A1	Flat	[-45, 45]	Between [-45] and [45] See fig. 4	-	Free standing	3
B1	Flat	[-45, 45, 90, 0, 90]s	Between Layer 1 [-45] and 2 [45] See fig. 4	Net-resin (no bleed)	Auto-clave	3
B2	Flat	[-45, 45, 90, 0, 90]s	Between Layer 1 [-45] and 2 [45] See fig. 4	Bleed-out	Auto-clave	3
C1	Spar See figure 1	[-45, 45, 90, 0, 90]	Between [-45] and [45] in area L and between all layers in area J. See fig. 5	Net-resin (no bleed)	Auto-clave	3

Table 3 Results

* Also seen in SEM graphs which are not included here.

Sample ID	MWCNT area	MWCNT deformation	Comment
A1	mid	Limited buckling & local shear	See fig. 7a and 7b *
B1	mid	Limited buckling & local shear	See fig. 7a and 7b *
B2	mid	Limited buckling & local shear	See fig. 7a and 7b *
C1	L (web)	Buckling & local shear	See fig. 7a and 7b *
C1	J (recess area)	Shear type 1 to 4 and combination of mechanisms	See fig. 7c to 7g *

Fig. 1 C-shaped spar with a recess area

Fig. 2 Shear in the recess flange during forming of [-45, 45, 90, 0, 90] lay-up.

Fig. 3 Definition of fibre directions.

Fig. 4 MWCNT placement in sample A1, B1 and B2

Fig. 5a MWCNT placement in sample C1.1, L= Web area, J= Recess area

Fig. 5b MWCNT placement in sample C1.2 and C1.3, L= Web area, J= Recess area

Fig. 6 Resin bleed out in samples to the left and no resin bleed out due to sealed laminate edges in samples to the right.

Fig. 7a MWCNT deformation - buckling

Fig. 7b MWCNT deformation - local shear

Fig. 7c MWCNT deformation - shear type 1

Fig. 7d MWCNT deformation – shear type 2

Fig. 7e MWCNT deformation – shear type 3

Fig. 7f MWCNT deformation – shear type 4

Fig.7g MWCNT deformation – combination of mechanisms